

CELLULAR AND ANTIBUBBLE ACOUSTICS

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Biological cells and microscopic antibubbles have got so much in common under sonication, that we thought it justified to organise a dedicated session on this topic.

Since the first photographic observation of antibubbles, it has been speculated that the antibubble core droplet can be loaded with therapeutics, which is to be released inside a tumour with the aid of ultrasound. Nowadays, antibubbles are commercially available and their sizes are on the order of those of ultrasound contrast agent microbubbles. Consequently, the first studies have been published on loading liquids inside the acoustic bubbles. Furthermore, a multitude of studies has been undertaken, both theoretically and experimentally, to predict the dynamics of antibubbles, with special focus on disruption thresholds.

This is where red blood cells come in: Although the acoustic regime, i.e., natural frequency and oscillation amplitude, is quite different from that of our everyday antibubble, both red blood cell and antibubble express expansion-only behaviour in a sound field.^[1]

For both, the incompressible liquid contents prevent contraction of the oscillating entity. The expansion-only behaviour of either antibubbles or red blood cells created a distinctive acoustic signature. In this presentation, we are providing optical experimental results of antibubbles and red blood cells under sonication at diagnostic ultrasonic settings. We show disruptive behaviour and interaction owing to radiation forces.

Furthermore, we demonstrate that antibubbles and red blood cells are interesting tracers in harmonic imaging.

Keywords

Antibubbles, harmonics, cellular acoustics, expansion-only behaviour

References

^[1] D.M. Rubin, N. Anderton, C. Smalberger, J. Polliack, M. Nathan, M. Postema. On the behaviour of living cells under the influence of ultrasound, *Fluids*, 3, 82 **2018**, 1-19.